

ISSUES OF UPBRINGING IN THE WORK OF KABUSNOMA BY KAYKOVUS

Hamrayeva Oynisa Farxadovna

Teacher of the department of pedagogy of Fergana State University

Muhamedova Mohidil Axrorovna

Student of the faculty of physical culture of Fergana State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10571891>

Annotation: this article reflects on the upbringing of a child, on the duties of the child before the parents, on the exhortations that the parents give to the child.

Key words: form, work, education, upbringing, truthfulness, hospitality, friendship, thoughts of thinkers, people.

Today, special attention is paid to our youth, education. Education and upbringing took a special place in the development of the younger generation as a perfect, mature person. The great Abdullah Avlani says about upbringing: "upbringing is either a matter of life-or of death, or salvation-or of destruction, or of happiness-or of disaster for us".

At present, we are using the works of our allies and their aids to educate young people. Education with training is similar to the two wings of a bird. If a person does not have upbringing, education cannot be shaped either. Upbringing is given to children from the mother's womb. Parents grow their child by washing them white from birth and combing them white, no less than someone else. Great importance is attached to their upbringing. In this regard, our ancestors have long been recommending ways, methods of upbringing, education in their works. An example of this is the work of Caicovus, "Kabusnoma". This work is considered a moral-educational work that is widespread among the peoples of East and Central Asia. The work was written by the author in reference to his son. The "Qobusnoma" admonishes upbringing, education, rosy, friendship. The author encourages his son to write down this work and follow the exhortations in it, thinking about the future of tomorrow. The main part of the work is the Quroni Karim suras, a work composed of the hadiths of our prophets. The work consists of 44 chapters. Each chapter contains the exhortations necessary to raise children as perfect people.

A large part of spiritual education is derived from spiritual values, including the pand-admonition of our ancestors. This pand-admonition and the oghites are reflected in the scrolls in the books left to us from them. A truly educated reader, on the other hand, is able to easily distinguish a book from others, which

is spiritually nourishing and capable of elevating its spirituality. Reading books of this content, on the other hand, is as if equivalent to enjoying a conversation between scientists and scientists. In particular, among the books of such content can be included the work of Caicovus "Kabusnoma". Alas today, many of our young people are unaware of the content of this book, when we say that this is exactly the same fact that some young people blindly, knowingly and understandably follow the "mass culture".

The content of this book is such that King Caicovus, with his life experiences, wants to raise his son Gilon the king, and claims these pandemics of his own as the most valuable inheritance for his son. In his work, the "Kabusnoma", he refers to his son Gilon the King, saying: "O child, my hope is that you will receive these pandas. It is known that the custom of the people is such that, running and looking and looking, they form something from the world and leave their things to their loved one. I have formed these words in the world, you are the most precious treasure for me. The time of the journey approached me, and whatever I have produced from the world, I have placed before you, so that you do not place a building on yourself, nor do you do things that are inappropriate to you."

In King Caicovus ' "Kabusnoma", issues of upbringing, morality are central. The book has 44 chapters. The author sets out an extremely important point in the chapter "on the respect of parents", using in this place a popular proverb of our people "what do you eat, what do you wrap". According to him, when a person does good to the people, respects the elders, favors the little ones, his good deeds will return from others, and his deeds will certainly return to him from others, even if he does evil and diligence. Caicovus further admonishes his son in this chapter: "... if you want your own child to respect you, put your parents ' respect in place, so that the way you treat them, let me return to you in the same way". In doing so, he encourages the parents not to hurt them, but to respect them, and to be polite with shirinso.

Caicovus encourages his son to approach the people, to pursue his interests, to his child: "see a lot of the little good of the people, he has reaped which thing stands close to the good of the people." Caicovus considers upbringing as one of the factors that shape human intelligence and personal life, while paying special attention to upbringing in his work. In this, he promotes the elevation of the human psyche, seeks the causes of negative vices. In particular, in the upbringing of a person, it is a duty to recognize that upbringing has a high role of influence in life. He believes that the goal of educating young people is to grow

them into individuals suitable not only for today, but also for the future. Therefore, the author pays special attention to the behavior, temperament of young people in the work. Also covered issues such as how to treat the enemy. The child, as it was said from the beginning, mentioned the need to raise a child from birth, teach the norms of etiquette, make science and skill, to form the child's skills in labor, otherwise without any effect of "late" upbringing, it would not give the necessary effect. The "Kabusnoma" states that it is the same provision to gain knowledge of all the strength in youth, to spend on vocational training.

Taking into account the above, our young readers will essentially enrich their spirituality by reading works of such content in their free time. Today, a wide range of opportunities has been created for young readers, who can understand the works they want by reading them in an electronic option. The peaceful and prosperous tomorrow of society depends above all on the education that our young people are receiving, mastering. Whichever apartment, neighborhood, family upbringing is well established, the same apartment, neighborhood, family will be a blessing to harmony when they find it. In itself, the prosperity and freedom of the land will also strengthen and rise.

"Kabusnoma" "gives these exhortations about the payment of parental rights: "o child, know that it is important to respect and honor the father and mother to the child through reason. Do not disappoint the parents for what I respect, know that they will also be prepared for your death".Indeed, the parents are also ready to give their lives for their child, there are also children who do not think about their parents. When a guilt works, he immediately comes to his parents and asks them to help him. Without telling him why you did this after the parent also had a child, the guilt will not help him even if he is in his son[8].The work of the acute Hoshimov" works of the world " is a work dedicated to mothers. In it, the mother is waiting for her child until the night before, when she returns from work late. The son came and said, " mother, Why didn't you sleep?", the mother replies, "Oh Baby, Sleep Is Recorded". When the son falls ill, in the cold he is picked up and taken to the healer.

That's when the mother ventilates her leg and becomes legless. Here you see that the mother will recover from her child without thinking about it in the cold

he keeps his foot ventilated by thinking. But now some children immediately forget about what their mother did. Therefore, each of us must reach the value of our parents, take their blessing and please. In this world, for a

child, the parent will not be the eldest, and for a parent, the child will not be the eldest. This work," Kabusnoma", contains exhortations about waiting for a guest: "o child, do not guest strangers every day, because if you receive a guest every day, you will not be able to indulge in what is worthy of the guest. Let the human heart call many times every month, call once if you want, make once the cost you will do, let the language of your table be innocent and those who seek guilt depend."

In our people there is such a proverb: from the door when the guest comes, from the hole where the provision comes. We are considered the hospitable people of the Uzbek people. We all love to wait for a guest. Did the guest come home, he will come with his sustenance, God will send with his sustenance. As long as there is a tree, a bird will land on it, as long as there is a house, of course, a guest will come. The guest is considered to be a noble for us. Everyone who is waiting for a guest should be a good-natured, open volunteer. Each house from which the visitor comes is blessed. "Kabusnoma" "also reflects on being a friend:" o child, one is alive, not without friends. It is better for a person to be a brother than without friends. The more each person has a friend, the more mystery their guilt is". Alisher Navoi, the Great Master of the word, quotes this quote about a friend:

"A friend will know that he will not know what he has not seen. He himself does not make his friend a partner in this case, even if he is ready to die for his friend."

It is permissible to cite the parable of Aesop about a friend. In the parable, a shepherd releases his goats into the pasture. At one point, the goats graze with wild goats. He locks them all in a cave when it's too late. The next weather is poor, so he grazes in a cave and feeds his goats to Nomi, spilling them abundantly on wild goats.

When the goats are released the next day, they flee towards the mountain. The shepherd suspects them to be noncookers who do not know the good. He says I did not feed you better than my goats. Then wild goats, so we must also walk away from you. We are going to you, and you will say that you have seen us better than your goats. From this example, we need to get the idea that we need. We must not forget the old ones when we make new friends. We should not rush to be friends with the undays either. When we make new friends, we also become old ones. Each of us must separate a friend-that enemy.

Friend pitifully speaks,
The enemy laughed.

A friend speaks the truth about his affairs in a serious tone. And the enemy makes him laugh and speak. Even through this proverb, we can distinguish a friend-enemy. The work "Kabusnoma" "admonishes childcare by saying," O man, if you have a child, put a good horse on him. Because one of the parents' fees to the child is to put a good horse. Then, after you have made your studies grander, if you are good-natured, you will teach him science and craft. You bring up your son with knowledge and skill.

There is such a proverb in our people:

One year old without science.

Everyone gives advice on how to give him knowledge in the care of a child, how to master science. He teaches the trades he needs for his child. The great Hadith scholar grandfather Imam al-Bukhari quotes Hadiths about learning and teaching science:

"Knowledge is classified into three groups to learn and teach knowledge. The first is that a person learns the knowledge of God and is interested in it. He himself learns, teaches others, such a person is considered a believer.

The second is that a person learns science, teaches people, but does not practice it himself. Such men are the wicked-the third, he does not learn, he does not teach others, such men are considered unbelievers". It is necessary to study science in order to marry it in life, without learning that one day it will be suitable for any kind of illness. When learning science, it is necessary to study well with good intentions. To master science, a person must have two things: one - meditation, the other-conservation. These two properties must be enhanced at times.

In place of the conclusion, it should be said that first of all, the parent should pay serious attention to the upbringing of his child. When a child is brought up well from childhood, they grow up to be a future child who does not face their parents on the ground, making their name known to the world. An educated person enters into circulation with any person. It is necessary to listen to the speech of adults in public places, listen carefully to their opinion. This also testifies to the good upbringing of the child.

List of literature used:

1.Hamrayeva, O. F. Q. (2023). OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASASI TALABALARINI KOMMUNIKATIV KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING AYRIM JIHATLARI. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 3(1), 537-544.

- 2.Hamroyeva, O. F. (2023). OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASASI TALABALARINI KASBIY-KOMUNIKATIV KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 3(4), 985-991.
- 3.Abdixakimovich, X. K. (2023). PEDAGOGIK HAMKORLIK ASOSIDA BO 'LAJAK OFITSERLARDA FUQAROLIK KOMPETENSIYASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH. Science and innovation, 2(Special Issue 12), 538-541.
- 4.Ergasheva, N. M. (2023). MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM TASHKILOTI RAHBARLARINING KOGNITIV KOMPETENTLIGI. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 3(11), 697-702
5. Hamrayeva, O. F. Q. (2023). OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASASI TALABALARINI KOMMUNIKATIV KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING AYRIM JIHATLARI. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 3(1), 537-544.
6. O.F.Hamrayeva,Sh.Ibrohimov. (2023). PEDAGOGICAL COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE AND WAYS OF ITS DEVELOPMENT. Ethiopian International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research, 10(12), 760-761. Retrieved from <https://www.eijmr.org/index.php/eijmr/article/view/834>
7. O.F.Hamrayeva, & Ibrohimova Shahnoza Shuhratjon qizi. (2023). ALISHER NAVOIYNING ASARLARIDA TA'LIM TARBIYA MASALALARI. THEORY OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCHES OF WHOLE WORLD, 3(3), 49-53. Retrieved from <https://esiconf.com/index.php/TOSROWW/article/view/599>
- 8.Hamroyeva, O. F. (2023). OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASASI TALABALARINI KASBIY-KOMUNIKATIV KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 3(4), 985-991.
- 9.Abdixakimovich, X. K. (2023). PEDAGOGIK HAMKORLIK ASOSIDA BO 'LAJAK OFITSERLARDA FUQAROLIK KOMPETENSIYASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH. Science and innovation, 2(Special Issue 12), 538-541.
- 10.Ergasheva, N. M. (2023). MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM TASHKILOTI RAHBARLARINING KOGNITIV KOMPETENTLIGI. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 3(11), 697-702
11. O.F.Hamrayeva, & Bozorova Fotimaxon Jo'rabek qizi. (2023). OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASASI TALABALARIDA AXLOQIY VA ESTETIK TARBIYANI RIVOJLANTIRISH. MODERN PROBLEMS IN EDUCATION AND THEIR SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS, 7(7), 9-12. Retrieved from <https://esiconf.com/index.php/mpe/article/view/598>
12. O.F.Hamrayeva, & Nozimova Dilfuza Jahongir qizi. (2023). OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASLARI TALABALARIDA FUQOROLIK TARBIYASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH.

THEORY OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCHES OF WHOLE WORLD, 3(3), 45–48.
Retrieved from <https://esiconf.com/index.php/TOSROWW/article/view/595>

